

Correlation Between Of Lipid Profile And Progression Of Oral Cancer In The Population Of Madhya Pradesh

¹Dr. Devashree Shukla, ²Dr. Dhaval N. Mehta, ³Dr. Chandresh Shukla, ⁴Dr. Gurinderjeet Singh Gulati, ⁵Dr. Ankit Dhimole, ⁶Dr. Dilraj Singh

¹Dr. Devashree Shukla

Phd Scholar , Department Oral Medicine Radiology, Narsinbhai Patel Dental college and Hospital, Sankalchand Patel University, Visnagar, Gujrat, Bhopal (MP)

Devashreeshukla17@Gmail.Com

²Dr. Dhaval N. Mehta

Phd Guide, Professor and Head , Department of Oral Medicine Radiology, Narsinbhai Patel Dental College and Hospital, Sankalchand Patel University, Visnagar, Gujrat,

drdhaval80@gmail.com

³Dr. Chandresh Shukla

Professor, Department of Orthodontics And Dentofacial Orthopaedics, Peoples College of Dentistry And Research Centre, Bhopal (MP)

chandresh1024@Gmail.Com

⁴Dr. Gurinderjeet Singh Gulati

Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Rishiraj College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre. Bhopal, MP.

dr_gurinder@rediffmail.com

⁵Dr. Ankit Dhimole

Reader, Department of Oral Medicine Radiology, Hitkarini Dental College & Hospital, Jabalpur

drankitdhimole@gmail.com

⁶Dr. Dilraj Singh

Senior Lecturer, Department of Oral Medicine Radiology, Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre, Gwalior.

dilraajsinghgwl@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Oral cancer is the rising public health concern in India, particularly in central state of India; Madhya Pradesh where tobacco consumption is prevalent and this habit is common among both males and females. Alterations in lipid profile have been associated with tobacco consumption and cancer pathogenesis, which could be potentially served as biomarkers for oral cancer risk.

This study evaluates and compares lipid profiles among tobacco chewers, oral cancer patients, and a healthy control group. A total of 450 participants were divided into three groups: Group A (tobacco chewers), Group B (healthy controls), and Group C (oral cancer patients). The findings revealed significant variations in lipid profiles, indicating a probable relationship between lipid metabolism and oral cancer development.

INTRODUCTION

In India oral cancer accounts for 30% of total cancer which is rising every year, incidence rate of this disease is expected to be 20 per 100,000 population. It has a high gender bias with male being affected at least three times as often as females. Factors such as tobacco chewing, tobacco smoking, and alcohol play an important role in development of oral cancer and potentially malignant disorders like OSMF, Lichen planus. Such habits are common in males than females. Although oral cancer in females is also associated with consumption of tobacco. It is believed that the initiation and progression of these conditions involves production of free radicals. Free-radicals are highly reactive species that could be found in the nucleus as well as membranes of cells and are instrumental in causing damage to DNA, proteins, carbohydrates and lipids.¹⁻⁴ Lipids are essential biomolecules for maintenance of various biological functions including stabilization of deoxyribonucleic acid helix, cell growth and division in normal as well as in malignant tissues.⁵The requirement of lipid for growth and proliferation of cancer cells alters the lipid values in an individual.⁶ The decrease in the level of cholesterol has been associated with an increased risk of cancer. Changes in lipid profile have been associated with malignancy because of their key role in the maintenance the integrity of the cell membrane. The development of a malignancy requires uncontrolled and excessive proliferation of cells. As the neoplastic disease is related to new growth, there is a greater utilization of lipid, including total cholesterol (TC), lipoproteins and triglycerides (TGs) for new membrane biogenesis. In this study correlation between lipid profile and its association with progression of oral cancer is done.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aims and Objectives:

- To evaluate if any of the abo blood groups are associated with an increased risk of oral cancer
- To evaluate serum lipid profile in patient having habit of tobacco consumption
- To assess whether serum lipid could be used as biomarker for Oral cancer
- To estimate serum lipid profile in different histological grades of Oral cancer

Study Population: A total of 450 participants from Madhya Pradesh were included.

- Group A: 150 tobacco chewers.
- Group B: 150 healthy controls.
- Group C: 150 oral cancer patients.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Group A: Habitual tobacco chewers without oral cancer.
- Group B: Healthy individuals without tobacco habits.
- Group C: Diagnosed cases of oral cancer confirmed histopathologically.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals with systemic diseases affecting lipid metabolism.

- Sample Collection and Analysis: Fasting blood samples were collected to analyze total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). Lipid- blood is centrifuged for 15 mins at 3000rpm to separate the serum, it is done on chemical analyzer based on spectrometric principle.⁶

RESULTS

Association between LDL and TNM Staging

LDL	TNM staging			Total	Chi square test
	T1-T2	T2-T3	T3-T4		
Low <100mg/dl	14	19	13	46	$\chi^2=15.161,$ df=6, p=0.019
Mod high (100-129mg/dl)	26	12	8	46	
High (130-159mg/dl)	13	9	9	31	
Very high	8	5	14	27	
Total	61	45	44	150	

Association Total cholesterol between and TNM Staging

Cholestrol	TNM Staging			Total	Chi square test
	T1-T2	T2-T3	T3-T4		
Low	10	8	7	25	$\chi^2=0.9615,$ df=6, p=0.987
Mod high	16	11	10	37	
High	17	14	16	47	
Very high	18	11	12	41	
Total	61	44	45	150	

Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in lipid profiles between the groups. Oral cancer patients exhibited the most pronounced dyslipidemia, followed by tobacco chewers.

DISCUSSION

LDL is a key component of lipid metabolism, and its levels are often altered in cancer patients. Dysregulated lipid metabolism may contribute to cancer progression by supporting rapid cell proliferation and membrane synthesis.¹ TNM staging reflects tumor size (T), lymph node involvement (N), and distant metastasis (M). The association between LDL and TNM staging may indicate significant results establishing its positive relation with alterations in LDL levels are linked to tumor growth, invasion, or metastatic potential. Low LDL levels in progressing cancer stages could result from increased lipid uptake by tumor cells. LDL levels could serve as a potential biomarker for assessing tumor stage and progression in oral cancer patients. There is no significant result associated with HDL and tumour progression, stating there is no direct association of HDL and growth potential of oral cancer p value 0.07. The elevated levels of triglyceride, VLDL, total cholesterol have not significant value in the association with cancer staging, these levels however effects tumor biology indirectly, also associated with metabolic disfunction and systemic inflammation.⁸The dysregulation of these values may not be associated with staging of oral cancer but indirectly impacts tumour growth and inflammation.⁷⁻¹⁵

CONCLUSION

The findings suggest that lipid profile alterations may serve as early indicators of oral cancer risk. Total cholesterol, HDL, VLDL and Triglyceride may not contribute to predispose direct association with cancer development but low level of low density lipids are significantly related with tumour staging as there is uptake of lipids by tumor cells for rapid cell growth. Thus significant p value 0.019 shows the correlation between LDL and Tumour staging, as the staging advances there is reduction in level of LDL, depending on the size of tumour thus indicating the rapid demand of low density lipids by tumor cells for growth.

Keywords: Oral cancer, lipid profile, tobacco, dyslipidemia, biomarkers, Madhya Pradesh

REFERENCES

1. Chawda J, Jain S, Patel H, Chawda H. The relationship between serum lipid levels and the risk of oral cancer. *Indian Journal of Medical and Paediatric Oncology*. 2011 Jan-Mar;32(1):34-37.
2. Tarsariya VM, Mehta DN, Raval N, Patadiya HH, Vachhrajani K, Ashem A. Evaluation of serum immunoglobulin (IgG, IgM, IgA) in potentially malignant disorders of oral cavity - A case control study. *J Oral Biol Craniofac Res*. 2020 Oct-Dec;10(4):665-669. doi: 10.1016/j.jobcr.2020.09.002
3. Kashyap P, Mehta T, Raval C, Manek PV, Kewalia K, Guruprasad Y, Arya S. Clinical Correlation of Types and Forms of Smokeless Forms of Quid (Tobacco and Arecanut) and Occurrence of Oro Mucosal Lesions: A Cross-Sectional Study. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2024 Jul;16(Suppl 3):S2182-S2184. doi: 10.4103/jpbs.jpbs_135_24.
4. Sargaiyan V, Singh S, Shukla R, Tanwar AS, Mehta T, Manek PV, Patel BJ, Patel KJ. Hematological profile of OSMF patients with increasing severity. *Bioinformation*. 2024 Apr 30;20(4):353-357. doi: 10.6026/973206300200353.
5. Sangle VA, Chaware S, Pawar S, Gawande M. Alterations in serum lipid profile in oral cancer and oral submucous fibrosis patients: A clinicopathological study. *Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology Journal*. 2013 Jul-Dec;4(2):385-390.
6. Garg D, Singla N, Garg S, Atreja G, Gupta S. Serum lipid profile in oral precancer and cancer: A diagnostic or prognostic marker? *Journal of International Oral Health*. 2014 Apr;6(2):33-39.
7. Lohe VK, Degwekar SS, Bhowate RR, Kadu RP, Dangore SB. Evaluation of correlation

- of serum lipid profile in patients with oral cancer and precancer and its association with tobacco abuse. *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine*. 2010 Feb;39(2):141-148.
8. Schatzkin A, Hoover RN, Taylor PR, Ziegler RG, Carter CL, Albanes D, et al. Site-specific analysis of total serum cholesterol and incident cancers in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey epidemiologic follow-up study. *Cancer Research*. 1988 Jan 15;48(2):452-458.
 9. Aarti G, Swamy M. Alterations of serum lipid profile in oral submucous fibrosis. *International Journal of Research Studies in Medical and Health Sciences*. 2017 Oct-Dec;3(4):1-5.
 10. Swamy MK, Arathi K, Kaur N. Evaluation of serum lipid profile in oral submucous fibrosis patients: A case-control study. *International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery*. 2017 Oct;3(4):1064-1067.
 11. Soundarya R, Ramesh G, Prabhakar R, Pradeep L. Evaluation of serum lipid profile and complete hemogram in patients with oral submucous fibrosis: A case-control study. *Journal of International Oral Health*. 2020 May;12(5):427-431.
 12. Boringi M, Bontha S, Guttikonda VR, Thupili S, Kambalyal P, Chandu VC. Lipid profile in patients with oral submucous fibrosis, lichen planus, and leukoplakia. *Journal of Indian Academy of Oral Medicine & Radiology*. 2016 Oct-Dec;28(4):375-380.
 13. Pratap M, Sinha A, Singh S, Singh RK. Estimation of serum lipid profile in patients with oral submucous fibrosis. *Journal of Indian Academy of Oral Medicine & Radiology*. 2015 Apr-Jun;27(2):139-144.
 14. Mehrotra R, Pandya S, Chaudhary AK, Kumar M, Singh M, Shukla P. Serum lipid profile in oral submucous fibrosis: A clinico-pathological study. *Lipids in Health and Disease*. 2009 May 6;8:29. [DOI]
 15. Aruna DS, Prasad KV, Shavi GR, Ariga J, Rajesh G, Krishna M. Retrospective study on risk habits among oral cancer patients in Karnataka, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*. 2011;12(6):1561-1566.